

THE ROLE OF THE TECHNICAL COMMUNITY IN THE INTERNATIONAL
MANAGEMENT OF MATERIALS

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It is a pleasure and privilege for me to speak to you tonight as the representative of the Federation of Materials Societies. In the view of the Federation, this Conference is not only important but highly gratifying since four of the sponsoring societies are members of the Federation and the others are participating in its programs. The purpose and objectives of this Conference, its multi-society sponsorship and the cooperative participation of eight prominent technical societies is a perfect example of what the Federation is all about. Of even greater significance is the international scope of this meeting for it confirms the increasing world recognition of materials as the underpinning of modern society.

Since many of you may not be too familiar with the Federation of Materials Societies and what it does, a brief description may be appropriate. The Federation is an association of professional and technical societies, representing over 500,000 scientists and engineers, concerned with the world shortages of raw materials and energy and the opportunities for the conservation of these natural resources through the management of materials. Better known by its acronym, FMS, the Federation was founded in 1972 and eleven societies are now members. The purpose of FMS is to assist its member societies in identifying problems and opportunities for cooperative action and coordinating their contributions to the solution of materials related issues.

Present members of FMS are: American Ceramic Society, American Chemical Society, American Institute of Chemical Engineers, American Society for Metals, American Society for Nondestructive Testing,

Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers, National Association of Corrosion Engineers, Society of Manufacturing Engineers, Society of Plastic Engineers, The American Society of Mechanical Engineers and the Metallurgical Society of AIME.

My objectives this evening are three-fold. The first is to strengthen your appreciation of the vital and growing importance of materials science and engineering in these critical and changing times and emphasize the unprecedented challenges and responsibilities and the equally unprecedented opportunities for materials scientists, engineers, managers and educators.

The second is to tell you something of the purpose and activities of the Federation of Materials Societies and illustrate how it can magnify the effectiveness and impact of the technical community on matters of materials policy and management that can contribute to societal well being.

The third is to encourage your consideration of the need for new mechanisms to promote and encourage closer international interaction and cooperation among the various disciplines that could enhance the value and impact of the international technical community on materials related issues of world importance.

Materials are a keystone of civilization. With energy and information they form the tripod that supports modern industrial society. Let one of these forces weaken or fail, and the structure of society is endangered or falls down. I know that there are many observers who would prefer the substitution of "environment" for "information" in my triad, but I do not. Environment is too often a subjective condition whereas information is, or should be, objective in nature and therefore overriding. The interrelationships and interactions of materials and energy are highly complex and are becoming increasingly so. Therefore ever increasing information is essential to their understanding and management.

Materials and energy are our natural resources. They are components of everything we produce and their importance in our personal lives and the economy of nations cannot be overemphasized. For too long, most industrialized nations, and particularly the United States, have assumed the unlimited availability of raw materials and energy and have thoughtlessly accepted their benefits. The Arab oil embargo of 1973 has changed all that.

However, for all of the dislocations and hardships produced by the energy crunch, the embargo may prove to have been a real blessing in that it severely jarred our complacency. At last, industry, government and the general public have awakened to the reality that our natural resources are finite in supply and cannot continue to support our infinite demand.

A recent report of the National Academy of Science, "Materials Technology in the Near-Term Energy Program", points out that, "of all short range approaches toward energy independence for the United States, conservation of energy offers the most promise". And it concludes that, "the opportunities for energy conservation through materials management are clearly tremendous". Certainly, informed and innovative management of materials over their total life and energy cycles can provide the most effective, economic and socially viable solution to the conservation of critical natural resources. No energy policy can be effective, over the long range, that does not have an integrated and compatible materials policy.

The first report is that of the National Commission on Materials Policy entitled "Materials Needs and the Environment Today and Tomorrow". The Commission was established by Congress to develop a national materials policy and make recommendations on supply, use, recovery and disposal of materials. Because of the increasing concern for environmental protection, the NCMP study emphasized the need for more effective management of materials policy by recognizing the complex interrelationships of the materials - energy - environment system. It warned that continued economic growth requires rising materials production and that securing sufficient supplies of materials means meeting a variety of economic, political, social, technological and environmental challenges.

The second report is that of the Committee on the Survey of Materials Science and Engineering, better known as COSMAT. COSMAT was established by the National Academy of Sciences and charged with conducting a comprehensive analysis and assessment of the fields of materials science and engineering. The overall objectives of COSMAT were: "To determine the nature and scope of science and engineering in the field of materials for the successful translation of new basic knowledge into useful applications; to examine the interaction of materials science and engineering with other areas of science and technology; to discern trends in the development of the materials field in order to identify its challenges, opportunities and needs; and to reach conclusions concerning the means by which materials science and engineering might contribute more broadly to the national well being".

As Professor Morris Cohen of M.I.T. and the chairman of COSMAT so well puts it, "materials technology has all the ingredients for catching popular interest in the future - a total body of science and engineering that can be invoked in a sophisticated - perhaps unprecedented-manner to help solve societal problems". This is our challenge and in it lies our opportunity. We have the capacity not only to contribute to the development of new sources of energy and materials, but to conserve their total and finite supply by maximum efficiency in their use. We have a major responsibility in making the recommendations and decisions that critically affect the amount of energy and materials used in the products society needs or

demands. While we must continue to work within the constraints of cost-value relationships, these relationships are now far less constraining than in the past. The term "cost-effective" takes on new dimensions when the total life and energy cycles of materials must be considered.

It would be fool hardy not to recognize that the new constraints of energy and raw material shortages and environmental concerns will impact on our traditional life styles. Our future is going to be different, but it does not necessarily follow that it is going to be bad. We have not even begun to mobilize our technical and management competence to solve our materials, energy and environmental problems. COSMAT represents a call to action, summarized in its five general thrusts:

1. The purposeful mobilization of the technical expertise of materials scientists and engineers.
2. A comprehensive federal leadership.
3. An intensive effort by industry to exploit and nourish the reservoir of materials knowledge.
4. A strengthened academic base to inject new knowledge into that reservoir.
5. A deliberate assumption of pertinent responsibilities by materials professionals and their technical societies.

The breadth of interests and areas of competence represented at this Conference are ample evidence of the multidisciplinary nature of materials science and engineering. Today, more than a half-million scientists and engineers are working in the field in the United States alone. The great majority of them still identify with their original disciplines of chemistry, physics or some type of engineering rather than with the materials community. They are served by more than thirty-five national professional and technical societies and, as COSMAT points out, often must belong to several to cover their individual needs. This fragmentation is not surprising when it is recalled that materials science and engineering is concerned with the generation and application of knowledge relating to the composition, structure, and processing of materials to their properties and uses.

The Federation of Materials Societies serves as a focal point for action on materials issues of common cause and concern to the technical community. It serves as a forum for discussion of matters broader than those that could be embraced by any single society, and provides a mechanism for voluntary cooperative efforts to achieve national goals. It serves those purposes without infringing the responsibilities and prerogatives of its constituent societies.

One of the very important functions of the Federation is to provide a mechanism for a continuing communication linkage between the materials community and the federal government that facilitates a collective input to the legislative and administrative policy-making process and feedback from the government to the materials community. Information is what governments need to make sound policy decisions. A task of the materials community is to help translate needs into terms which governments and the public can understand. Its importance is emphasized by the fact that over 140 separate bills on materials management, shortages, stockpiling and recycling were introduced in the United States Congress last year.

Early in its life, the Federation was requested by the National Commission on Materials Policy to study the subject of conservation of materials. It did this and integrated the inputs from 16 societies into a compact report with conclusions and recommendations. This report served as one of the bases for the NCMP report. It has been printed in member society journals and widely distributed.

Currently, at the request of the Congressional Office of Technology Assessment, the FMS committee on Materials Information is preparing a survey of existing institutions providing the various kinds of United States materials information services, with an appraisal of their scope, quality, accessibility, completeness and adequacy relative to estimated national need. This committee has also just completed a pamphlet on "Sources of Technical Information on Materials". It lists some forty organizations that gather, analyze and disseminate information and data on materials. This pamphlet will soon be made available to FMS member societies and other interested groups at a small nominal charge for printing.

Recently, the Federation, in cooperation with several other organizations and with support from a number of prominent scientists and engineers in government and industry, have been exploring the concept of an "International Materials Year" for 1977. It is felt that an International Materials Year might serve a number of purposes. For example: It could bring world wide attention to the importance of materials and materials science and engineering. It might help ease the tensions resulting from mismatches of materials supply and demand and provide impetus toward systematic and rational interdependence among nations in the field of materials management and knowledge.

While an International Materials Year would have finite life, it could provide the basis for continuing mechanisms to consider world materials problems and address opportunities for materials science and engineering to contribute to solutions to other world problems and thus to the betterment of mankind.

Multi-society sponsored conferences, such as this one on composite materials and the programs and activities of the individual

sponsoring societies and other professional organizations, can help us in the coordination of our individual efforts. I believe the Federation of Materials Societies provides the mechanism for uniting the efforts of the technical community and enhancing its impact on government, industry and society.

The flow of materials between nations ties advanced and developing nations together. The solution of economic and social problems increasingly requires consideration of materials in terms of their complex path between nations. I believe that new mechanisms are needed to assure effective international interaction and cooperation on materials issues of world importance. An International Materials Year may provide the basis for such a mechanism.

Thank you for inviting me to speak to you.